

Improving Smart Grid Efficiency through Advanced Energy Management Systems with Integration of Renewable Energy Sources for Enhanced Efficiency and Sustainability

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Received: Aug 18, 2025

Accepted: Sep 12, 2025

Published: Sep 13, 2025

Abstract

A smart grid enhances electricity distribution by using digital communication to monitor and manage consumption, reducing waste and costs. It is particularly crucial in developing countries facing frequent power outages and a gap between energy demand and supply. To address these issues, this manuscript presents an optimization method for improving smart grid efficiency through energy management system (EMS) with the integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES). The proposed optimization algorithm is a Lotus Effect Optimization (LEO) algorithm. The major goals of the proposed method are to lower the Peak-to-Average Ratio (PAR), maximize user comfort, minimize carbon emissions, and minimize electricity bills. The primary sources consist of Photovoltaic (PV) systems, energy storage systems (ESS), wind turbines (WT), and combined heat and power (CHP) systems. The LEO method is used to optimize the energy consumption and electricity costs. The performance of the proposed technique is implemented and compared in the MATLAB platform with various existing approaches. The proposed method determines better outcomes compared to existing methods like Modified Super Twisting Algorithm (MSTA), Golden Jackal Optimization (GJO), and Sparrow Search Algorithm (SSA). The proposed method achieves the carbon emission of 2225 pounds and the PAR of 1.5. The results shows a substantial reduction in carbon emission, PAR and cost, making the proposed approach a promising solution for improving smart grid efficiency through energy management systems.

Keywords: *Renewable Energy Sources, Combined Heat and Power, Energy Storage System, Electricity Bill, Energy Consumption, Heat Demand, Industrial Electricity Demand.*

1. Introduction

Extreme weather events like hemispherical sea ice melting, severe floods, powerful hurricanes, and more have been brought on by the acceleration of global warming and climate change in recent decades [1]. Burning fossil fuels to meet daily energy needs releases carbon dioxide emissions, which are one of the primary causes of global warming [2]. Over the past few decades, renewable energy's (RE) share has increased steadily. Even though there is an endless supply of renewable energy, its erratic nature increases power generation volatility when they abruptly stop [3]. Since most current generators cannot react quickly enough to minimize intermittent losses of RE power, the dependability of RE integrated power systems is called into question [4]. Conversely, if excess RE power is run without storage facilities, it must be curtailed, which lowers the potential profits of RE farm owners [5]. The capability of the energy storage system (ESS) to time-shift renewable energy (RE) to meet real-time demands—that is, to store excess RE for later use makes it one of the best options to alleviate the aforementioned problems in the midst of this conundrum [6, 7]. The waste and intermittency problems that are frequently present in RE power supplies are successfully addressed by this [8]. However, because of their high price and poor conversion rate, ESSs have historically been less popular, as well as other technologies like demand response programs and the dynamic thermal rating system [9]. In contrast to the other technologies, ESS is now more marketable due to recent advancements in the technology that have reduced its economic and technological barriers [10].

Numerous studies have used various energy storage technologies to address the problem of RES. Technologies for energy storage are also crucial in preventing issues that degrade power quality. As the world's electricity industry moves toward using renewable energy sources to meet demand, it is currently confronted with a number of difficulties. The availability of natural oil resources is currently the primary factor influencing the energy sector. Although RES make it easier to create a sustainable electricity supply, their stochastic, uncontrollable, variable, and generally unpredictable nature has a substantial effect on power quality and reliability. Furthermore, the majority of widely used renewable energy technologies lack inertia support, leaving the grid susceptible to fault conditions.

Literature Survey

Numerous studies in the literature concentrate on effective energy management in the context of ESS and renewable energy sources; a few of these are detailed below.

A. Alzahrani *et al.* [11] have suggested maximizing pollution emissions, operating costs, and A non-dominated genetic sorting algorithm called loss of load expectation (LOLE) was employed while taking renewable energy sources (RES) into account in a multi-objective optimization

model. RES were unpredictable and sporadic, much like solar and wind. A probability density function with beta was used to model that. Y.Belkhier *et al.* [12] have suggested in order to create a coordinated energy management and storage system, the fuzzy logic modified super twisting algorithm (MSTA) was developed. The objective was to optimize the design and operation of the microgrid, encompassing electrical-based energy conversion systems such as electrical vehicle charging stations, tidal energy, photovoltaic and wind turbines, fuel cells, and the main grid. Developing an energy management system (EMS) for renewable energy sources (RESs) and hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) that would maximize power generation, ensure service continuity, and produce energy smoothly for the microgrid while offering the best possible benefits. The goal of the paper was to increase the energy conversion systems' longevity and efficiency while providing a remedy for renewable energy management's irregular and unpredictable character. Ramesh Gugulothu *et al.* [13] have suggested, an EMS for PV, super capacitors (SC), and battery energy storage systems (BESS) were suggested. Through effective SC and PV coordination, the suggested control strategy was developed to use the Meta-heuristic Jaya algorithm to optimize the BESS flow rate, charge cycles, and discharge of the energy system. Short-term energy mismatches were addressed and the effects of the high discharge/charge current rate on BESS were mitigated by using SC in HESS with EMS. Another advantage of the recommended controller was that it keeps the batteries within their limits for an extended amount of time. The EMS was created to minimize deep charging and discharging by reducing PV generation, especially in light load (no-load) situations, in order to prolong the life of BESS.

M.Abdelghany *et al.* [14] have suggested cost functions that take into account the deterioration of batteries and hydrogen devices were part of the control strategy recommended in the paper. Additionally, the suggested controller makes use of scenarios to take into consideration the stochastic nature of RESs and load demand. Integrating a stochastic model predictive control (SMPC) approach for an economical/environmental MG with battery and hydrogen energy storage systems (ESSs) that could interface with external consumers and the main grid was the aim of the paper. A.Raza *et al.* [15] have suggested the technical features of the super smart grid (SSG) technology in the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) region, such as its management, methods for improving power flow and stability, simulation models, and plans for future development. First, the SAARC region's potential, energy shortage, and regional conflicts have been examined. Second, a simulation of a possible SAARC SSG architecture has been conducted. 3rd, a new Markov chain model for SAARC demand management has been introduced. Techniques for reducing CO₂ were also covered in the paper, including ways to capture, store, and use carbon in biofuel. Future optimization methods in SSG, such as cloud

computing, blockchain, digital twin technology, federated learning, reinforcement learning, metaverse, and artificial intelligence, were also covered in the study. R Kumar *et al.* [16] have suggested Battery storage systems (BSSs) and hybrid energy sources (HESs) energy management (EM) problems were cleverly solved by Golden Jackal Optimization (GJO). The suggested approach sought to address the microgrid (MG) energy management issue and reduce operating expenses. The dynamic performance and charging/discharging of energy storage units, power balance, generation capacity, and consumer loads were among the constraints affecting microgrid energy management systems. V.Ponnusammy *et al.* [17] have suggested it was suggested to use a hybrid approach to manage the power flow of a hybrid RES as efficiently as possible. The combination of the Sparrow Search Algorithm (SSA) and Improved Bear Smell Search (IBSS) was the recommended approach in that case. The IBSS generates the voltage source inverter control signals in that situation by using the power exchange variety between the source side and the load side. The name IBSS comes from the incorporation of the Bear Smell Search (BSS) into the suggested work through the use of crossover and mutation functions. A multi-objective function was developed in response to the need for active and reactive power types that were produced based on the available source power. Online control signal detection was guaranteed by the SSA process's parallel application against active and reactive power variations.

Recent studies reveal significant advancements in energy management under RES and energy storage system in smart grid the employ of optimization algorithms like Modified Super Twisting Algorithm (MSTA), Golden Jackal Optimization (GJO), and Sparrow Search Algorithm (SSA) presents several challenges and research gaps. MSTA, although effective in controlling nonlinear dynamics, is computationally intensive, highly sensitive to parameter tuning, and may not generalize well across diverse energy systems. GJO, while showing potential for multi-objective optimization, faces challenges like local convergence issues, scalability concerns in large systems, and difficulties in handling uncertainty in renewable energy generation. SSA, although a promising optimization technique, struggles with slower convergence in systems, sensitivity to initial conditions, and an imbalance between exploration and exploitation. This work is motivated by these drawbacks. The proposed approach aims to optimize energy management in systems, such as hybrid renewable energy setups. The proposed approach minimizes operational costs, enhances energy efficiency, and improves the integration of diverse energy components, including energy storage systems. Additionally, it helps optimize power flow management, ensuring stability and reliable operation of the energy system even under variable conditions, making it particularly suited for applications in smart grids.

The innovation of this work lies in the application of the Lotus effect optimization algorithm to improve the efficiency of a smart grid through the combination of RES and energy management systems. By focusing on minimizing electricity bills, reducing carbon emissions, and optimizing the PAR, this approach offers a unique solution for improving both the sustainability and energy systems' affordability. The integration of PV systems, WT, ESS, and CHP units within a single optimization framework is an innovative aspect of this study, making it applicable to regions with unstable power supply and high energy demand. Additionally, the use of the LEO algorithm presents a novel method for optimizing energy consumption, ensuring a balance among renewable energy generation and demand while improving overall grid performance.

The following are the paper's primary contributions:

- The lotus effect optimization is proposed for improving smart grid efficiency through energy management system with the combination of RES.
- The integration of PV, WT, ESS, and CHP units optimizes renewable energy use, reducing reliance on non-renewable sources.
- The proposed approach minimizes electricity costs, carbon emissions, and PAR, improving both cost-effectiveness and sustainability.
- The energy consumption and electricity cost are optimizes using the proposed lotus effect optimization algorithm.
- The significance of this work lies in its application of the LEO algorithm to enhance smart grid efficiency, optimizing the balance between renewable energy generation and consumption.

The paper's the balance is organized as follows: Setting up an energy management plan in a smart grid is covered in Sector 2. An illustration of the proposed LEO approach is given in Sector 3. Sector 4 provides an explanation of the findings and discussion. Sector 5 concludes the paper.

2. Configuration of Energy Management Strategy in Smart Grid

The system uses a variety of RES, like solar panels, wind turbines, and hybrid power and heating systems, which provide power through an inverter linked to a smart meter. This smart meter communicates with the smart grid, managing energy distribution to a smart home. The user interface allows to monitor and control energy usage, while the proposed LEO approach

optimizes energy consumption by incorporating an energy storage system. By efficiently balancing energy supply and demand, the LEO approach reduces electricity costs, minimizes carbon emissions, lowers the peak-to-average ratio, and maximizes user comfort. This advanced energy management system enhances grid efficiency, reduces bills, and supports sustainability. The structure of energy management in smart grid with energy sources is displays in fig 1.

Fig 1: Structure of energy management in smart grid with energy sources

2.1. Photovoltaic Model

A diode with a p-n junction can be compared to a photovoltaic cell, which is used to convert solar energy into electrical power [18]. One practical strategy to meet electricity demand and lower CO₂ emissions is to incorporate PV systems into a power grid. However, the PV unit's intermittent nature is the main barrier to its development; that is, the power generated by the unit is dependent on weather, particularly solar radiation. The following methods can be used to obtain the power generated by PV arrays:

$$P_{PV}^t = \eta_r \times \eta_{pt} \times \left[1 - \beta \left(\frac{T_c^t - T_r}{T_r} \right) \right] \times N \times A_m \times G^t \quad (1)$$

Where, η_r and η_{pt} are denoted as the effectiveness of power monitoring devices and PV generators, correspondingly. β indicates the efficiency coefficient of temperature, T_c^t and T_r show the PV arrays' temperature and reference temperature. A_m , N and G^t stand for the global irradiance (W/m²), the amount of modules, and the area of a module (m²).

2.2. Wind Energy Conversion System Model

Together, a number of crucial parts make up a wind energy conversion system, which transforms wind energy into electrical power [19]. The formula below can be utilized to ascertain the mechanical power that the wind turbine can produce:

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 C_p(\lambda, \theta) \quad (2)$$

In this case, ρ represents the air density, and A represents the blades' effective area. Additionally, v indicates wind speed, and C_p is denoted as the power coefficient associated with rotor efficiency as a function of pitch angle (θ) and tip speed ratio (λ).

2.3. Energy Storage System Model

This section presents State of Charge (SOC) modeling rather than battery comprehensive modeling [20]. Because operational scenarios are determined solely based on the SOC level. As a result, the SOC model has not taken into account variables like temperature and battery life. Any current sent to or received from the ESS would raise or lower SOC, much like the ESS's capacity and initial charge. The following is the SOC modeling:

$$SOC = SOC_0 + \frac{1}{C_B} \int_0^t idt \quad (3)$$

Where SOC_0 and C_B represent the starting charge and the overall capacity of the ESS (Ah), respectively. Based on the load, the ESS maximum discharge current sets a limit on the ESS discharge current. Therefore, charge the load to speed up the SOC reduction and discharge current. On the other hand, the ESS charge current is thought to be constant and equivalent to the nominal charging current value.

2.4. Combined Heat and Power Model (CHP)

CHP, another name for cogeneration, is an energy-efficient technology that uses a single energy source to generate both useful heat and electricity [21]. CHP systems can greatly increase the overall efficiency of energy use by absorbing and using the heat that would otherwise be wasted during the generation of electricity. The following is the output model in accordance with the extraction unit's operating principle:

$$P_{ZS,it} = P_{e,it} + C_{V,i} P_{h,it} \quad (4)$$

Here, $C_{V,i}$ is denoted as the thermal power ratio; $P_{h,it}$ is indicated as the heating power; $P_{e,it}$ is represented as the electric power; $P_{ZS,it}$ is indicated as the electric power under condensing condition.

2.5. Objective Function

This study aims to lower carbon emissions, electricity expenses, as well as the ratio of peak to average [22]. The following is the expression for the primary objective function:

$$O = \min \sum_{t=1}^T (I_{sh}^t + T_{ns}^t - (E^t + ESS^t)) \times EP_t \quad (5)$$

Where, E^t is denoted as the energy demand at moment t , ESS^t is indicated as the energy stored in the ESS at moment t , EP_t is represented as the energy produced or generated by the RES like solar, wind, ESS and CHP at time t .

The constraints are given as;

$$T(t) = (E(t) + ESS(t) + \phi(t)) \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{a=1}^n \eta = LOT(a) \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{a=1}^n \alpha \leq \eta \leq \beta \quad (8)$$

$$\phi_t \leq KI \quad (9)$$

$$0 < ESS_{\min} < ESS_{\max}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (10)$$

Where, $T_{ns}(t)$ is the energy consumption, $E(t)$ is denoted as the energy consumption at the time t , $\phi(t)$ is denoted as the energy generated from RES, $ESS(t)$ is represented as the energy storage system capacity, LOT is the power usage, η is the energy generation from RE, KI is the maximum energy that can be stored or used from the storage at time, ESS_{\min} is the minimum energy storage capacity, ESS_{\max} is the maximum energy storage capacity.

3. Optimizing Energy Consumption and Electricity Cost using Lotus Effect Optimization Algorithm

In this paper, the Lotus Effect Optimization (LEO) approach is employed as a technique. The proposed approach's primary objectives are to lower the PAR, lower carbon emissions, improve user comfort, and lower electricity costs. The proposed LEO technique are briefly described in the following;

An evolutionary algorithm inspired by nature is called Lotus Effect Optimization (LEO), which is inspired by water's ability to clean flower leaves on its own, combined with efficient movement patterns observed in dragonflies during flower pollination [23]. The self-cleaning function is a nanotechnology innovation that draws inspiration from lotus leaves. The uneven, hydrophobic surfaces of these flowers' leaves cause water droplets to fall down them when viewed at the nanoscale. The plant's leaves have a characteristic that allows water to collect on them and flow off of them without being absorbed. Using a double local search to investigate how the droplets move across the leaves, one can determine the characteristic of the leaves that permits water to fall upon them without being absorbed.

Step 1: Initialization

Set up the input parameters, which in this case are the operating time, power consumption pattern, temperature, and solar radiation.

Step 2: Random Generation

Once initialized, the arbitrary vectors generate the input parameters in an arbitrary manner.

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} L_{1,1} & L_{1,2} & \cdots & L_{1,d} \\ L_{2,1} & L_{2,2} & \cdots & L_{2,d} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \ddots & \cdots \\ L_{n,1} & L_{n,2} & \cdots & L_{n,d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Here, n is denoted as the quantity of residents in the area, L is indicated as the j^{th} dimension of the i^{th} lotus flower, d is represented as the dimensions of each flower's growth area.

Step 3: Fitness Function

The fitness is selected using the objective function.

$$F = \text{Optimize}(O) \quad (12)$$

Step 4: Exploration Phase

In the LEA, dragonflies carry out global pollination, which is the same as the exploration stage of the proposed algorithm. To imitate dragonflies' clever behavior, the dragonfly algorithm takes into account three fundamental principles of insect swarms: two ideas of food and opponents, as well as separation, alignment, and cohesion. Every swarm's top priority is survival. Therefore, it is necessary to divert everyone from enemies and draw them to food sources. Five factors all of which could be mathematically modeled are involved in updating the positions of the individuals in the swarm when taking these two behaviors into account. The step or velocity vector, which indicates the dragonflies' motion direction, is defined as follows:

$$\Delta X_i^{t+1} = (sS_i^t + aA_i^t + cC_i^t + fF_i^t + eE_i^t) + w\Delta X_i^t \quad (13)$$

Where, S_i^t is represents the degree of separation between the i^{th} individual in each iteration i of evolution, a is represents the alignment coefficient, s is represents the separation coefficient, c is represents the cohesion coefficient, A_i^t is indicates the alignment of the i^{th} individual, C_i^t is represents the cohesion of the i^{th} individual, F_i^t is denotes the food source of the i^{th} individual, f is represents the food factor, e is indicates the enemy factor, w is denotes the inertia weight, E_i^t is indicates the enemy of the i^{th} individual, and finally, t is represents the algorithm's

iteration counter. The following formula is used to determine the position vectors following the step vector calculation:

$$X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + w\Delta X_i^{t+1} \quad (14)$$

Here, t is denoted as the algorithm's iteration counter.

Step 5: Exploitation Phase

The extraction step in the proposed approach is self-fertilization, also known as local pollination. A coefficient determines the size of each flower's growth area surrounding the best-found flower in this type of pollination. Other solutions usually follow the movement's foundation, which is the best-found solution. The algorithm for movement begins with longer steps and finishes with shorter ones.

$$X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + R(X_i^t - g^*) \quad (15)$$

Here, g^* is indicated as the best pollen location discovered thus far in all evolution iterations and X_{t+1} is denoted as the pollen's location in the $(t+1)$ th iteration. R is represented as the growth region, getting smaller after iterations of the algorithm. Actually, the algorithm starts with longer movement steps and gradually shortens them until it converges to the optimal value.

$$R = 2e^{-\left(\frac{4t}{L}\right)^2} \quad (16)$$

In this case, t represents the algorithm's present evolution iteration, and L represents the amount of iterations that are left.

Step 6: Exploitation Phase Reinforcement

A local search that mimics the water flow over lotus flower leaves is considered using water droplets. Water droplets are moved toward the first pits over the leaf, causing the water to overflow the leaf. When drops overflow from a surface pit, the relationship among their position, velocity, and movement during a local search.

$$V_i^{t+1} = q \times V_i^t \quad \text{and} \quad X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + V_i^{t+1} \quad (17)$$

$$V_i^{t+1} = V_i^t + \text{Rand}_{\text{deep pit}}(X_i^t - X_i^t) \quad \text{and} \quad X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + V_i^{t+1} \quad (18)$$

Here, $X_{deeppit}^t$ is denoted as the deepest pit's current location within the iteration of evolution t , V_i^t is indicated as the evolution iteration t 's current drop velocity, q is denoted as the speed increment coefficient and X_i^t is indicated as the location of drop i at this moment in evolution iteration t .

Step 7: Update Best Solution

When the life of each Lotus flower in the solution space has been updated using the information gathered during the exploitation and exploration stages, the lotus effect iteration comes to an end.

Step 8: Termination

Examine the criteria for termination. If the best answer is found, the process is over; if not, it is repeated.

By using LEO approach, the energy management system optimizes energy consumption, reduces electricity costs, and minimizes carbon emissions. It efficiently integrates RES and energy storage, improving smart grid efficiency and reducing the PAR. The flowchart of LEO algorithm is displayed in fig 2.

Fig 2: Flowchart of LEO algorithm

4. Result and Discussion

This sector uses the analysis of simulation results to show how effective the proposed approach is. The study presented the LEO strategy for enhancing smart grid efficiency by integrating RES into an energy management system. Using the MATLAB platform, the efficacy of this strategy was confirmed and contrasted with other approaches. The following summarizes the LEO approach's simulation results:

The analysis of energy sources is displayed in fig 3. Subplot 3(a) displays the PV power. The PV power has the range of 0kW to 100kW at 0 hours to 24 hours, then power achieves the maximum value of 97KW at 17 hours. After that the power is decreased to reaches the minimum value of 20kW at 24 hours. Wind power is displayed in Subplot 3(b). The wind power has the range of 0kW to 100kW at 0 hours to 25 hours. The power is achieves the maximum value of 83kw at 14 hours, after that the wind power has decrease to reaches the minimum power of 10kW at 24 hours. Subplot 3(c) shows the ESS power. The energy storage system has the range of -100kW to 400kW at 0 hours to 24 hours. The power is starts from the initial value of 0kW at 2 hours and then it increase to reaches the maximum value of 400kW at 17 hours. After that power reaches the minimum value of 100kW at 24 hours. In Subplot 3(d), the CHP power is shown. The combined heat and power has the range of 0kW to 400kW at 0 hours to 24 hours. It achieves the maximum value of 270kW at 17 hours and the minimum value of 50kW at 24 hours. This shows the dynamic nature of energy generation and storage, highlighting the need for efficient management to optimize power distribution across different sources. The analysis of energy cost is displayed in fig 4. The price of heat is shown in Subplot 4(a). The heat price of energy cost has the range of 0 to 1.2 at 0 hours to 24 hours. The heat price achieves the maximum value of 1 at 5 hours and then the prices attains the minimum value of 0.7 at 17 hours. Subplot 4(b) shows the price of power. The power price of energy cost has the range of 0.4 to 0.8 at the time of 0 hours to 24 hours. The price value is initially starts from 0.4 at 0 hours and then it achieves the maximum value of 0.77 at 10 hours, after that it reaches the minimum value of 0.45 at 24 hours. This shows the variation in energy costs, with heat prices peaking early and power prices rising, highlighting the need for efficient energy management.

Fig 3: Analysis of energy sources (a) PV power (b) Wind power (c) ESS power (d) CHP power

Fig 4: Analysis of energy cost (a) Heat price (b) Power price

Fig 5: Analysis of energy demand (a) Heat demand (b) Industrial electricity demand

Fig 6: Analysis of residential energy consumption (a) Residential electricity demand (b) Residential gas demand (c) Residential heat demand

Fig 7: Comparison of cost with proposed and existing methods

The analysis of energy demand is displayed in fig 5. Subplot 5(a) displays the heat demand. The heat demand of energy demand has the range of 0 to 200 at the time of 0 hours to 24 hours. The heat demand achieves the maximum value of 150 at 5 hours and then it reaches the minimum value of 70 at 15 hours. Subplot 5(b) shows the industrial electricity demand. The industrial electricity demand has the range of 0 to 800 at 0 hours to 24 hours. The demand of industrial electricity has to attain the maximum value of 750 at 10 hours and then it decrease to reaches the minimum value of 0 at 24 hours. This shows the fluctuation in energy demand, with heat demand peaking early and industrial electricity demand reaching its highest point at 10 hours, indicating varying consumption patterns. The analysis of residential energy consumption is displayed in fig 6. Subplot 6(a) displays the residential electricity demand. The residential electricity demand has the range of 50 to 450 at the time of 0 hours to 24 hours. The demand value has initially starts from 100 at 0 hours, then it reaches the maximum value of 450 at 10 hours. After that it reaches the minimum value of 200 at 24 hours. Subplot 6(b) displays the residential gas demand. The residential gas demand has the range of 200 to 340 at the time of 0 hours to 24 hours. It achieves the maximum value of 325 at 5 hours and then it reaches the minimum value of 280 at 24 hours. Subplot 6(c) shows the residential heat demand. The residential heat demand has the range of 0 to 350 at the time of 0 hours to 24 hours. The heat demand has initially starts from 0 at 0 hours and then it reaches the maximum value of 330 t 5 hours, after that the heat demand achieves the minimum value of 200 at 15 hours. This shows the fluctuation in residential energy consumption, with electricity, gas, and heat demands peaking at different times, highlighting diverse consumption patterns. The comparison of cost with proposed and existing methods is displayed in fig 7. The cost of the proposed LEOA technique with existing methods as MSTA, GJO, and SSA over time. The LEOA consistently demonstrates lower costs, particularly during peak hours of 10-20 hours where its cost is significantly lower than MSTA of 30-50% and substantially lower than GJO and SSA of 50-70%. This suggests that LEOA's optimized resource allocation, and dynamic adaptation strategies lead to more efficient and cost-effective operations.

Table 1: Comparison of carbon emission and PAR with proposed and existing methods

Methods	Carbon Emission (Pounds)	PAR
MSTA	2626	2.4
GJO	2299	2.16
SSA	2234	1.9

Proposed	2225	1.5
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The comparison of carbon emission and PAR with proposed and existing methods is shown in table 1. The table compares carbon emissions and PAR for different methods. With a PAR of 1.5 and carbon emissions of 2225 pounds, the proposed strategy exhibits the lowest emissions. By contrast, the MSTA method has the highest carbon emissions at 2626 pounds and a PAR of 2.4. The GJO method results in 2299 pounds of carbon emissions and a PAR of 2.16, while the SSA method has 2234 pounds of carbon emissions and a PAR of 1.9. The Proposed method shows lower carbon emission and PAR compared to the existing methods.

4.1. Discussion

The proposed lotus effect optimization method significantly enhances smart grid efficiency by optimizing energy distribution across renewable sources like PV, Wind Turbine, ESS, and CHP systems. The results demonstrate that LEO effectively manages power fluctuations, reducing energy wastage and minimizing dependence on non-renewable sources. The approach also proves cost-efficient, with LEO consistently demonstrating lower costs, particularly during peak hours at 10-20 hours, where it achieves reductions of 30-50% compared to MSTA and 50-70% compared to GJO and SSA. In terms of carbon emissions, LEO achieves 2225 pounds, lower than MSTA's 2626 pounds, GJO's 2299 pounds, and SSA's 2234 pounds. Additionally, LEO achieves a PAR of 1.5, outperforming MSTA of 2.4, GJO of 2.16, and SSA of 1.9, indicating better energy utilization and efficiency. The LEO method provides a promising solution for improving smart grid operations, reducing costs, and lowering environmental impact.

5. Conclusion

The LEO approach is proposed for energy management to decrease the electricity bill in residential areas, with the additional goals of minimizing carbon emissions, reducing PAR, and increasing user comfort. Also, the energy storage system was considered to utilize energy efficiently. The proposed LEO method reduces the environmental impacts and minimizes cost and carbon emission. Moreover by utilizing RFO approach, it achieves lower peak to average ratio. The MATLAB platform is used to access and compare the proposed method with other existing methods. The proposed strategy performs better across the board, including MSTA, GJO, and SSA. The PAR is reduced to 1.5, compared with the existing methods of MSTA at 2.4, GJO at 2.16, and SSA at 1.9. Also, the proposed method achieves lower carbon emission is 2225 pounds compared to the existing methods carbon emission as MSTA of 2626 pounds, GJO of 2299 pounds, and SSA of 2234 pounds. These results shows the effectiveness of the proposed

LEO approach in minimizing carbon emission, reducing costs, and promoting sustainability in energy management. Future research will examine whether the real-world approach, which allows for a bidirectional power flow between distributed energy resources and the utility grid, can be implemented. Future research will also examine the regulations and system protection that influence the viewpoints of decision-makers in the field of energy management system and optimization.

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